

Do Crimes affect the Natural Resources? Nexus between Socioeconomic Factors and Corruption levels

Nesrin Topcu Tarakçı

Medipol University Health Sciences Institute, Turkey

Salma Nawaz

Department of law; University Law College, Quetta, Balochistan, Pakistan

Meryem Demirtaş

Health Management Department, Şırnak University, Turkey

Cumhur Sahin,

Bilecik Seyh Edebali University, Turkey

Yeter Demir Uslu

Faculty of Health Sciences, Medipol University Turkey

Yasemin Hancıoğlu Başköy

Department of Accounting and Taxation, Ordu University Turkey

Akram M. Hadded

Amity University Dubai, UAE

Malik Shahzad Shabbir (corresponding author)

Department of Management Sciences, ILMA University Karachi, Pakistan

ABSTRACT: South Asian region has enriched with different kinds of natural resources. This study is trying to examine the relationship between socioeconomic factors and different corruptions levels. For this purpose, the Panel Co-integration method is applied for empirical analysis by using annual data sets for the period 2005 to 2022. Furthermore, for the parameter estimation, we have applied Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) and Dynamic OLS (DOLS) models. Finally, the Police is considered one of the most corrupt departments in selected south Asian countries. The government of South Asian countries should take serious actions against the police and other departments in order to eliminate the corruption level among them.

Keywords: natural resources, Corruption; Crimes; Education level;

JEL Classifications: B21,

[Introduction](#)

[Literature Review](#)

[Methodology](#)

[Results and Discussion](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

Becker published a paper in 1968 that the way of thinking regarding criminal behavior fundamentally changes. Since the early 1980s, Becker's theory has opened up a new empirical ground of research whose main objective is to validate and study economic variables to identify agents' criminal behaviors and choices. Although corruption is indeed the main problem in almost all developing countries (lower scores), corruption still exists in some Western countries. Even all higher scores (Corruption Perception index, 2015)

cleanest economies are situated in the Western world. So the question, however, arises what are the significant determinants of corruption in developed as well as in developing economies? Similarly, why are developed and developing countries facing corruption, or why is corruption increasing over time in the whole world? The key objective of this is a research study to provide an answer to these questions and with using empirical analysis of the major determinants of corruption in developed and developing countries. Recently various research studies like Treisman (2000), Ali et al., 2022; Aslam et al., 2022; Ashraf and Shabbir 2019; Fahamsyah et al 2023; Xue et al 2024; Yan et al 2024; Liang et al 2023; Sikandar et al 2023; Nawaz et al., 2022; Hayat et al., 2022; Serra (2006), Majeed, and MacDonald (2010, 2011) used cross country analysis (Ehsan et al., 2022; Bai et al., 2022; Shabbir, 2021;).

Corruption in a structure is always a barrier to the honest allocation of resources in the context of economics (Lenka and Barik (2023)). As a result, combating corruption is a top concern for a country's growth. The primary goal of the research is to experimentally investigate the effects of financial integration on corruption control in chosen middle to upper-income nations. Using cross-country data from 2004-2018, the study evaluated the effects of monetary inclusion on corruption control throughout every sample nation. The research findings suggested that financial participation up to a specific threshold level aids in corruption control, while financial inclusion over the threshold level hinders corruption control.

This research contributes to the study of the main determinants of corruption in society by focusing on the corruption perceived index. It is probable that more corrupt and most clean nations react differently to various factors that encourage corrupt activities. Due to these differences in management institutions between the most corrupt and least corrupt countries, it might affect many essential determinants of corruption. This study is based on the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) definition of corruption as the exploitation of public officials for personal gain. Therefore, the study goal's is to investigate the impact of income, education, and inflation on corruption in South Asia. Thus, the contribution of this research is unique, which distinguishes this study from others and fills a gap in the literature by using the South Asian economy. The study contributes to the literature in the following ways, first, this study used social factors and their impact on corruption. Previous studies mostly focus on the cause and consequences of corruption. Second, the study is important because it shows the anti-corruption measures to reduce corruption. However, there are some studies focusing on income as an independent variable. The lower level of income leads to difficulty to fulfill the basic need of life.

2. Literature Review

On the basis of previous literature, the association between corruption and per capita income is gradually diminishing. There are two contradictory views on the idea of association, the point of view of clarity and the decrease of ability (Rehman and Naveed, 2007). Positive views of income to corruption convey the potential results of income that income gives a positive impact on corruption. People having more money always try to resolve their problems by all means. In this way, they utilize financial resources (Calderón,

Duncan, and Schmidt- Hebbel, 2016; Campos et al., 2010; Aslam et al 2024; Ahmed et al 2024; Qing et al 2024; Shabbir 2016; rehman et al 2023; Dreher and Schneider, 2010; Rotimi et al., 2013).

Many research works have shown that corruption is positively influenced by the level of income (Braun and Tella (2004); Frechette, (2001)). Lindner (2013) explored that many economies used the strategy of increase in income to reduce corruption, however, an increase in income does not always reduce corruption because good management and control of the system much need to reduce corruption (Lindner, 2013). However, there are many other studies such as Lederman et al. (2005), Braun and Di Tella (2004); Shabbir et al. (2021); Chang and Golden (2007); Nawaz et al. (2022); Kunicová & Rose-Ackerman (2005); Sikandar et al 2023; Shabbir et al 2023; Rawoof et al 2023; Ur Rehman et al 2023; Mughal et al 2023; Bhatti et al 2023; Tabasam et al. (2022); and Lederman et al. (2007) show that corruption is negatively influenced by the level of income. They showed that education not only enhanced the economy but also increase income distribution and reduced the level of corruption (Theo et al., 2009). Inflation is positively related to corruption. In other words, significant variations in prices have a rising impact on corruption (Braun and Tella., 2004). Corruption was seen as very high in those countries that have high inflation rates (Al-Marhubi, 2000). Same is the case, Smith-Hillman (2007), Abed and Davoodi (2002), Rohozyny and Sinitsina (2004), Shabbir, 2022; Nawaz et al., 2021; Bahmani-Oskooee and Nasir (2002), and Gupta and Chaudhuri (1997), in their studies, concluded that increase in overall prices leads to increase the level of corruption (Abed and Davoodi., 2002; Al-Marhubi and Fahim., 2000; Wang et al 2023; Liu et al 2023; Dabrovski, Rohozynsky, and Sinitsina, 2004). However, several studies used these adopted methods such as (Shabbir and Wisdom 2020; Shabbir 2018; Zhang et al., 2023;).

The study by Ishfaq and Waqas (2023) investigates the impact of corruption on GDP growth from 1996 to 2021. The data for the time series study comes from "WDI" and "Transparency International". The study used GDP as a factor of dependence. As independent variables, trade openness, inflation, and corruption were considered. There is a long-run connection between the variables, but no short run relationship exists. Empirical evidence suggests that trade openness has a positive impact. Further, their study inspected the causality between public debt, shadow economy and corruption. Nurjannah et al., 2023 investigate the elements that influence ASEAN integration and economic growth. The study's findings revealed that capital was responsible for a 0.248% influence, labor produced a 0.467% impact, human development provided a 3.010% effect, intra-regional trade showed a 0.014% effect, and control of corruption made a 0.260% benefit.

Kabir et al., (2023) research findings highlight the relevance of noneconomic drivers in reducing inflation, where constraints on corruption, the enforcement of law, and the efficiency of government have contributed to the decrease of pricing in Bangladesh. It should be focused on enhancing the standard of noneconomic achievements and highlighting the importance of those aspects through the consequences of laws and regulations, digitization, and assuring open-door activities and readily available information for every consumer of products and services. Further research should look at the additional noneconomic and macroeconomic factors that influence price increases in Bangladesh.

Dokas et al., (2023) after looking at the direct influence of corruption on the growth of the economy, looked into the indirect effect via several transmission routes, particularly innovation. Meanwhile, the research looks at how innovation affects the connection between corruption and growth in the economy. The findings revealed a strong negative association between economic growth and corruption, as well as corruption with innovation. The studies also demonstrated a positive association between development and economic growth, as well as reversible causality. Furthermore, it discovered that innovation can lessen the negative consequences of corruption on the economy, particularly in advanced nations.

3. Methodology

3.1. The Model

This study selects four south Asian countries such as (Bhutan, India, Nepal and Pakistan) for data analysis purposes. This study uses panel annual data set starts from 2005 to 2022. Therefore, this research estimates the following equation. The simple way of the panel data equation is shown below:

$$Cor_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PCGDP_{it} + \beta_2 ED_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where, *i* stands for cross sections of countries, and 't' denotes the time period (2005 – 2022)

The variables included in the analysis are:

Cor_{it} = Corruption

$PCGDP_{it}$ = Income Level

INF_{it} = Inflation

ED_{it} = Level of Education

μ_{it} = Error Term

Theoretical explanation and expected signs of independent variables are as follows:

Elevated levels of public pay may carry a more prominent ability to battle corruption, as explored by Blackburn et al. (2005). Whereas, Shabbir (2016), Paldam, (2001), Shabbir (2021) and Treisman, (2000) case debasement in developed nations are more grounded than in emerging economies bringing about assembly (all different variables held consistently) as the emerging nations find advanced nations at comparable degrees of per capita GDP after some time..

Inflation: The swelling has been found as an obstacle to monetary prosperity in a few exact examinations. The expansion makes twists, makes monetary shakiness, bringing about less beneficial financial movement, low financial development, and henceforth the need to control for swelling.

Level of Education: Education is negatively related to corruption which is recognizable in previous studies (Oreopoulos and Salvanes, 2009; Shabbir, 2018; Heyneman, 2002). As per the story, Training encourages perseverance and the ability to lose the present for better future gains, in light of the fact that understudies need to make a solid effort to get positions (Kaffenberger, 2012).

4. Results and Discussion

The curve indicates the presence of nonlinear relationships. The curve has increased significantly in the central corruption range and then decreased at the point where corruption is at least and the most. The nonlinear fitting line shows that the "hypothesis" of the "wheel" exists at the end of the corruption line, while the role of the "wheel" exists in the middle section of corruption.

Figure 1: Corruption and Level of Income of South Asia

Note: X-axis = corruption, and Y-axis = Per capita income

¹ Sources: WDIs and ICRG

Fisher/Johansen panel cointegration test

The trace test shows two cointegration vectors, whereas, at a level of 1%, the max Eigen test shows one cointegration vector. Table 1 shows the Fisher/Johansen test results, which indicate cointegration among factors as invalid theory is dismissed. Follow measurements show two co-combination vectors, whereas, at 1% criticalness level, max-eigen demonstrates one cointegration vector.

¹ Mughal et al (2023).

Table 1: Fisher/Johansen panel cointegration test

Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*		Fisher Stat.*	
No. of CE(s)	(from trace test)	P-value	(from max-eigen test)	p-value
None	61.11	0.000	40.74	0.000
At most 1	28.13	0.000	21.72	0.003
At most 2	11.44	0.078	11.08	0.123
At most 3	9.05	0.191	11.15	0.245

* Probabilities are calculated by authors with asymptotic Chi-square distribution.

Estimation of the model

Table 2 illustrates that a high literacy rate reduces the corruption level. The coefficient value shows that when education raises by 1%, corruption reduces by 2.74% (2.55%) in FMOLS (DOLS) estimations. Like the level of education, inflation also has a statistically significant but positive impact on corruption in South Asia. When inflation increases then corruption also increases. 1% increase in inflation corruption will increase 2.04% (1.649%) in FMOLS (DOLS) These findings are consistent with the previous literature; Babatunde et al., 2012; Kim and Lee, 2009; WaGithinji and Adesida, 2011; Lee, 2013; Fosu, 2013a; Asongu, (2016); Fosu, 2013; Kim, 2009; Lee, 2013; Piplica, 2011; Samimi et al., 2012; and Smith-Hillman, 2007).

The coefficient's sign of per-capita is negative, which indicates that an increase in per-capita income leads to a decrease in corruption in the region. The value of the coefficient shows that a 1% increase in per-capita income leads to a decrease in corruption by 2.24% (2.02%) in FMOLS (DOLS) estimation. Our current study's results are justified because similar results showed in previous studies (Dreher and Gassebner, 2013; Dreher and Schneider, 2010; Goel and Nelson, 2010; Okada and Samreth, 2012; and Swaleheen, 2011).

Table 2: FMOLS and DOLS estimations

Variable	FMOLS	DOLS
Level of Education	0.005** (-2.707)	0.016** (-2.75)
Inflation	0.042** (2.043)	0.127* (1.603)
Per-capita GDP	0.024** (-2.151)	0.034** (-2.025)
R-squared	0.86	0.851
Adjusted R-squared	0.82	0.811
S.E. of regression	0.174	0.171
***, **, * significant at 1%, 5% and 10%		
Parentheses values are t-values calculated by authors		

4.5. Robustness analysis

Furthermore, expansion has likewise gotten measurably decidedly unimportant. Per-capita gross domestic product negatively affects debasement. Gross domestic product (GDP) growth has measurably decidedly noteworthy in both FMOLS and DOLS assessments. The coefficient value of GDP growth in estimation shows that a 1% expansion in development builds defilement by 3.17% (2.71%) in FMOLS (DOLS)

assessments. Positive indications of development demonstrate that defilement increments because of expanded development.

Table 3. FMOLS and DOLS Estimations for Robustness Analysis

Variable	FMOLS	DOLS
Level of Education	0.023** (-2.31)	0.015** (-2.156)
Inflation	0.85 (0.21)	0.981 (0.006)
Percapita GDP	0.000** (-3.29)	0.003** (-3.066)
GDP Growth	0.002** (3.117)	0.008** (2.711)
R-squared	0.861	0.865
Adjusted R-squared	0.827	0.841
S.E. of regression	0.174	0.172

***, **, * significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

5. Conclusion

The current study is highlighting the aspects of life related to lower levels of income, and a person involves in illegal activity. In our study, we have tried to explore how corruption can be influenced by socioeconomic factors, especially income, education, and prices. Either there is a positive or negative, short run or long run impact of income, inflation, and education on corruption. Researchers explore all the variables separately but no clear evidence of their relationship.

This research study further suggests that government should not only take some solid actions against corruption but also there is need to create wealth, maintain the equal distribution of income and good opportunities for employment, and increase the level of income which should be as good as they can fulfill the needs to their families. Moreover, the government should do three important steps; one is to increase the minimum level of income as well as enhance the incentive of the worker to encourage their work, second thing, public reforms are required, especially, the government should convert the organizational system into a computerized system. Minimum involvement of humans leads to a decrease in the level of corruption, thirdly government should take steps to control the level of corruption by moral value. This step seems to be less attractive but this step can be the solution for a long time.

References:

1. Abed, M. G. T., & Davoodi, M. H. R. (2000). Corruption, structural reforms, and economic performance in the transition economies: International Monetary Fund.
2. Adam, B. M., Sarpong-Kumankoma, E., & Fiador, V. (2023). Economic freedom, corruption and bank stability: evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Financial Crime*.
3. Abed, G., & Davoodi., T. (2002). Corruption, Structural Reforms, and Economic Performance in the Transition Economies. *Governance, Corruption, & Economic Performance*.
4. Ahmed, S., Rameez, M. A., Fatima, H., & Usmani, H. (2016). Police officers gunned down while protecting vaccination workers in Pakistan. *J Infect Public Health*, 10(2).

5. Ahmad, M. N., Zhou, X., Muhammad, S., & Shabbir, M. S. (2024). Does green tax theory affect the environmental sustainability and protection?. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-11.
6. Aidt, T. S. (2009). Corruption, institutions, and economic development. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 25(2), 271-291. doi: 10.1093/oxrep/grp012
7. Akça, H., Ata, A. Y., & Karaca, C. (2012). Inflation and corruption relationship: Evidence from panel data in developed and developing countries. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 2(3), 281-295.
8. Al-Marhubi. (2000). Income inequality and inflation: the cross country evidence. *Contemporary Economic Policy*, 18(4), 369-490.
9. Al-Marhubi, & Fahim., A. (2000). Corruption and Inflation. *Economics Letters*, 66(2), 199-202.
10. Ashraf, Y., & Shabbir, M. S. (2019). An empirical investigation on brick and mortar attributes for the effective adaptation of online banking in Pakistan. *UW Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(2), 83-96.
11. Aslam, E., Farooq, U., Iqbal, A., & Shabbir, M. (2022). Comparative Risk Analysis of Sukuk and Bond: Insight From Arch and Garch Model. *Central European Management Journal*.
- 12.
13. Aslam, E., ur Rehman, A., Bhatti, F. A., Iqbal, A., & Shabbir, M. S. (2024). Investing In Goodness: Exploring Pakistan's Attitude Towards Participation In Cash Waqf. *Migration Letters*, 21(S6), 1500-1516.
14. Asongu, S. A. (2016). Determinants of growth in fast- developing countries: Evidence from bundling and unbundling institutions. *Politics & Policy*, 44(1), 97-134.
15. Asongu., S., A., & Nwachukwu., J. (2014). The Role of Lifelong Learning in Political Stability and Non-Violence: Evidence from Africa. *Ssrn Electronic Journal*.
16. Asongu., S., A., & Nwachukwu., J., C. (2015). The incremental effect of education on corruption: evidence of synergy from lifelong learning. *Working Papers*, 35(4), 2288-2308.
17. Attila, G. (2011). How do African populations perceive corruption: microeconomic evidence from Afrobarometer data in twelve countries. (200811).
18. Bahmani-Oskooee, & Nasir. (2002). *Economic Development and Cultural Change*.
19. Bahmani-Oskooee, M., & Nasir, A. (2002). Corruption, law and order, bureaucracy, and real exchange rate. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 50(4), 1021-1028.
20. Bai, D., Jain, V., Tripathi, M., Ali, S. A., Shabbir, M. S., Mohamed, M. A., & Ramos-Meza, C. S. (2022). Performance of biogas plant analysis and policy implications: Evidence from the commercial sources. *Energy Policy*, 169, 113173.
21. Baltagi, B. H., Feng, Q., & Kao, C. (2012). A Lagrange Multiplier test for cross-sectional dependence in a fixed effects panel data model. *Journal of Econometrics*, 170(1), 164-177.
22. Bao-yu, B., Xiao-xiao, L., Yu, K., & Frank, K. Belief in a Just World Lowers Perceived Intention of Corruption: The Mediating Role of Perceived Punishment. *Plos One*, 9(5), e97075-.
23. Becker, A., & Todd, M. (2017). Watching the evolution of the American Family? Amazon's Transparent, ecological systems theory, and the changing dynamics of public opinion. 1-18.
24. Beets. ((2005)). Understanding the Demand-Side Issues of International Corruption. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 57(1), 65.
25. Bhatti, F. A., Aslam, E., ur Rehman, A., Ashraf, S., Aslam, M., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). Does intellectual capital efficiency spur the financial performance of banks? A comparative analysis of Islamic and conventional banks in Pakistan. *Al-Qanṭara*, 9(3), 55-67.
26. Braun, M., & Di Tella, R. (2004). Inflation, inflation variability, and corruption. *Economics & Politics*, 16(1), 77-100.
27. Braun., M., & Tella., R. (2004). Inflation Variability, and Corruption. *Economics and Politics*, 16(3), 77-100. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0343.2004.00132.x
28. Breusch, T. S., & Pagan, A. R. (1980). The Lagrange multiplier test and its applications to model specification in econometrics. *The review of economic studies*, 47(1), 239-253.
29. Butalia, U. (2013). Poverty and corruption. *New Internationalist*(366), 5.
30. Barik, R., & Lenka, S. K. (2023). Does financial inclusion control corruption in upper-middle

- and lower-middle income countries?. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Regional Science*, 7(1), 69-92.
31. Calderón, C., Duncan, R., & Schmidt-Hebbel, K. (2016). Do good institutions promote countercyclical macroeconomic policies? *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 78(5), 650-670.
 32. Campos, N. F., Dimova, R. D., & Saleh, A. (2010). Whither corruption? A quantitative survey of the literature on corruption and growth.
 33. Chauhan, S., Banerjee, R., & Dagar, V. (2021). Analysis of impulse buying behaviour of consumer during Covid-19: An empirical study. *Millennial Asia*, 09763996211041215.
 34. Cheung, H. Y., & Chan, A. W. H. Corruption across countries: Impacts from education and cultural dimensions. *The Social Science Journals*, 45(2), 0-239.
 35. Cole, M. A. (2007). Corruption, income and the environment: an empirical analysis. *Ecological Economics*, 32(4), 637.
 36. Dabrowski, M., Rohozynsky, A., & Sinitsina, I. (2004). Post-adaptation growth recovery in Poland and Russia: similarities and differences. (280).
 37. Dreher, A., & Schneider, F. (2010). Corruption and the shadow economy: an empirical analysis. *Public Choice*, 144(1-2), 215-238.
 38. Dwiputri, I. N., Arsyad, L., & Pradipto, R. (2018). The corruption-income inequality trap: A study of Asian countries: *Economics Discussion Papers*.
 39. Dokas, I., Panagiotidis, M., Papadamou, S., & Spyromitros, E. (2023). Does innovation affect the impact of corruption on economic growth? International evidence. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 77, 1030-1054.
 40. Ehsan, S., Tabasam, A. H., Ramos-Meza, C. S., Ashiq, A., Jain, V., Nazir, M. S., ... & Gohae, H. M. (2023). Does Zero-Leverage Phenomenon improve Sustainable Environmental Manufacturing Sector: Evidence from Pakistani Manufacture Industry?. *Global Business Review*, 09721509221150876.
 41. Ekpo, A. H., & Agiobenebo, T. (1985). Corruption and prices: A theoretical note. *The Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 27(3), 305-316.
 42. Fajnzylber, P., Lederman, D., & Loayza, N. Crime and Victimization: An Economic Perspective. *Economía*, 1(1), 219-278.
 43. Fahamsyah, M. H., Mawardi, I., Laila, N., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). Global Islamic Banking Development: A Review and Bibliometric Analysis Using R-Biblioshiny Application. *Muqtasid: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Perbankan Syariah*, 14(1), 69-92.
 44. Fosu, A. K. (2013). *Achieving development success: Strategies and lessons from the developing world*: Oxford University Press.
 45. Frechette, G. R. A. P. D. A. o. t. T.-V. D. o. C. P. p. a. t. E. (2001). A Panel Data Analysis of the Time-Varying Determinants of Corruption. Paper presented at the EPCS, 22(3), 219.
 46. Goel, R. K., & Nelson, M. A. (2010). Causes of corruption: History, geography and government. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 32(4), 433-447.
 47. Gründler, K., & Potrafke, N. (2019). Corruption and economic growth: New empirical evidence. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 60, 101810.
 48. Hayat, K., Tabasam, A. H., Ali, A., Ashiq, A., Shabbir, M. S., & Rawoof, H. A. (2022). Relationship of challenge and hindrance stressors with turnover intention and employee's creativity: The moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Journal of Management Info*, 9(2), 146-157
 49. Hajdini, A., Collaku, L., & Merovci, S. (2023). Effect of corruption on foreign direct investment inflows in countries of the Western Balkans. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*, 9(1), 130-143.
 50. Hall, R. E., & Jones, C. I. (1998). Why Do Some Countries Produce So Much More Output per Worker than Others? Working Papers.
 51. Heyneman. (2002). Defining the Influence of Education on Social Cohesion. *International Journal of Educational Policy, Research and Practice*, 3(4), 73.
 52. Hough, D. (2016, January 27). Here's this year's (flawed) Corruption Perception Index. Those flaws are useful. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/monkey-cage/wp/2016/01/27/how-do-you-measure-corruption-transparency-international-does-its-best-and-thats-useful/>

53. Heyneman. (2008). Education, social cohesion and ideology. In *Right to Education: Policies and Perspectives*. Turkish Education Association. , 37(3), 89.
54. Hongdao, Q., Mumtaz, A., Mukhtar, H., Rahman Saleem, H. A., & Azam, S. (2018). Corruption prevention and economic growth: A mediating effect of rule and law. *Int'l J. Soc. Sci. Stud.*, 6, 128.
55. Hope, K. R. (2017). Police corruption and the security challenge in Kenya. *African Security*, 11(1), 84-108.
56. Isaksson, A. S., & Kotsadam, A. (2018). Chinese aid and local corruption ☆. *Journal of Public Economics*, 159.
57. Ishfaq, A., & Waqas, M. (2023). Impact of Corruption on Economic Growth in Pakistan: An Analysis. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 149-158.
58. Jungo, J., Madaleno, M., & Botelho, A. (2023). Controlling corruption in African countries: innovation, financial inclusion and access to education as alternative measures. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 50(6), 766-786.
59. Jensen, V. M., & Rasmussen, A. W. (2011). Danish education registers. *Scandinavian journal of public health*, 39(7_suppl), 91-94.
60. Jones, E. (1994). Lords of poverty : the power, prestige, and corruption of the international aid business. *Foreign Affairs*, 73(2), 146-155.
61. Jones, K. A. (2015). *Rent Seeking*: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
62. Kaffenberger., M. (2012). The effect of educational attainment on corruption participation in sub-Saharan Africa. Graduate School of Vanderbilt University.
63. Kabir, G. I., Fairuj, M., Montaha, S., & Uddin, M. M. (2023). Appraising the Impact of Rule of Law, Control of Corruption, and Govt. Effectiveness on Inflation: An Empirical Case of Bangladesh. *Global Sustainability Research*, 2(1), 1-9.
64. Khan, M. K., Babar, S. F., Oryani, B., Dagar, V., Rehman, A., Zakari, A., & Khan, M. O. (2022). Role of financial development, environmental-related technologies, research and development, energy intensity, natural resource depletion, and temperature in sustainable environment in Canada. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29, 622-638.
65. Kim, T. (2009). Confucianism, Modernities and Knowledge: China, South Korea and Japan *International handbook of comparative education* (pp. 857-872): Springer.
66. Kinda, M. T. (2011). Modeling inflation in Chad: International Monetary Fund.
67. Khan, M. B., Saleem, H., Shabbir, M. S., & Huobao, X. (2021). The effects of globalization, energy consumption and economic growth on carbon dioxide emissions in South Asian countries. *Energy & Environment*, 0958305X20986896.
68. Khuong, N. V., Shabbir, M. S., Sial, M. S., & Khanh, T. H. T. (2021). Does informal economy impede economic growth? Evidence from an emerging economy. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 11(2), 103-122
69. Kolokoltsov, V. N., & Malafeyev, O. A. (2017). Mean-Field-Game Model of Corruption. *Dynamic Games & Applications*, 7(1), 34-47.
70. Kunicová, J., & Rose-Ackerman, S. (2005). Electoral Rules and Constitutional Structures as Constraints on Corruption. *British Journal of Political Science*.
71. Lederman, D., Loayza, N., & Soares, R. R. (2007). *Accountability and Corruption: Political Institutions Matter*. Social Science Electronic Publishing.
72. Lee, K. (2013). How can Korea be a role model for catch-up development? A 'capability-based'view. *Achieving development success: Strategies and lessons from the developing world*, 25(34), 1.
73. Lee, K., & Kim, B.-Y. (2009). Both institutions and policies matter but differently for different income groups of countries: determinants of long-run economic growth revisited. *World development*, 37(3), 533-549.
74. Leff, N. H. (1970). Economic development through bureaucratic corruption. In *political Corruption: Readings in Comparative Analysis*.
75. Li, H., Xu, L. C., & Zou, H. F. (2000). Corruption, Income Distribution, and Growth. *Economics & Politics*, 12(2), 155-182.
76. Liang, X., Zhang, Y., Tan, J., Chen, H., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). The Dynamic Relationship Between Multidimensional Energy Poverty and Social Wellbeing's. *Social Indicators*

- Research, 1-14.
77. Liu, Y., Salman, A., Khan, K., Mahmood, C. K., Ramos-Meza, C. S., Jain, V., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). The effect of green energy production, green technological innovation, green international trade, on ecological footprints. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-14.
 78. Lindner, S. (2013). Salary top-ups and their impact on corruption.
 79. Lorme, C. D. D., Kamerschen, D. R., & Mbaku, J. M. (1986). Rent Seeking in the Cameroon Economy: Krueger's Analytic Technique Helps to Account for Development Lag in Colonial States. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 45(4), 413-423.
 80. Lui, F. (1985). An Equilibrium Queuing Model of Bribery Games. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93, 760-781. doi: 10.1086/261329
 81. Lui, J., D.C. (1985). A Equilibrium Model of Bribery. Manuscript Buffalo.: State Univ. New York, Dept. Econ.
 82. Mauro, P. (1995). The Effect of Corruption on Growth, Investment and Government Expenditure: A cross country Analysis. *Corruption and Global Economy*, 14(3), 186-198.
 83. Mauro, P. (1997). The Effect of Corruption on Growth, Investment and Government Expenditure: A cross country Analysis. *Corruption and Global Economy*.
 84. Meon, P. G., & Weill, L. Is Corruption an Efficient Grease? *Social Science Electronic Publishing*.
 85. Miller, S. (2016). Police Corruption.
 86. Mocan, N. (2008). What Determines Corruption? International Evidence From Microdata. *Economic Inquiry*, 46.
 87. Mughal, N., Zafar, S. Z., Rawoof, H. A., Maria, S. C., Zhilin, Q., Magdalena, R., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). The Dynamic Effects of Socioeconomic Factors on Different Crime Levels: Evidence from South Asian Countries. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1-14.
 88. Nawaz, S., Shabbir, M. S., & Koser, M. (2022). The dynamic analysis of Islamic laws regarding educated women's life in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Research*, 5(2)
 89. Nawaz, H., Hayat, K., Zehra, N., & Shabbir, M. S. (2022). Do the Financial Slacks Improve the Performance of Agribusiness? A Mediating Role of Corporate Social Responsibility Activities. *Journal of Finance and Accounting Research*, 4(2), 75-98.
 90. Hugo, E., Savage, D. A., Schneider, F., & Torgler, B. (2023). Two sides of the coin: exploring the duality of corruption in Latin America. *Journal of Institutional Economics*, 1-15.
 91. Owusu-Nantwi, V., & Owusu-Nantwi, G. (2023). Public debt, corruption and shadow economy in Africa: an empirical analysis. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 39(1), 184-202.
 92. Pesaran, M. H. (2004). General diagnostic tests for cross section dependence in panels.
 93. Pesaran, M. H. (2007). A simple panel unit root test in the presence of cross- section dependence. *Journal of applied econometrics*, 22(2), 265-312.
 94. Piplica, D. (2011). Corruption and inflation in transition EU member countries. *Ekonomiska misao i praksa*(2), 469-506.
 95. Qing, L., Yao, Y., Sinisi, C. I., Salman, A., Jaradat, M., Spinu, A. E., ... & Shabbir, M. S. (2024). Do trade openness, environmental degradation and oil prices affect green energy consumption?. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 52, 101342.
 96. Rawoof, H. A., Said, L. R., Irmak, E., Pelit, I., & Malik, S. S. (2023). The Dynamic effects of Foreign Direct Investment Services and Energy Consumption on Information and Communication Technology Sector. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 13(5), 553.
 97. Rehman, A. U., Malik, A. H., Shabbir, M. S., Hussain, A., & Raza, K. M. (2023). Does Sharia Tag Constitute Heuristic While Choosing an Islamic Financial Institute? Evidence From Pakistan. *GISRAS Journal of Management & Islamic Finance (GJMIF)*, 3(4).
 98. Rehman, A., Radulescu, M., Ma, H., Dagar, V., Hussain, I., & Khan, M. K. (2021). The impact of globalization, energy use, and trade on ecological footprint in Pakistan: does environmental sustainability exist?. *Energies*, 14(17), 5234.
 99. Reinikka, R., & Svensson, J. (2005). Fighting corruption to improve schooling: evidence

- from a newspaper campaign in Uganda. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 3(2-3), 259-267.
100. Rong, N., Xin-lan, W., Yu-guang, Y., Economics, S. o., & University, L. (2013). An Empirical Study on the Effective Demand of Policy-oriented Agricultural Insurance—Based on the Rural Household Survey Data in Liaoning Province. *Journal of Northeastern University(Social Science)*.
 101. Rotimi, E., Obasaju, B., Lawal, A., & IseOlorunkanmi, J. (2013). Analysis of corruption and economic growth in Nigeria. *Analysis of corruption and economic growth in Nigeria*, 4(4.2), 1-19.
 102. Samimi, A. J., Abedini, M., & Abdollahi, M. (2012). Corruption and inflation tax in selected developing countries. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 11(3), 391-395.
 103. Schreinemachers, P., Wu, M., Uddin, M. N., Ahmad, S., & Hanson, P. (2016). Farmer training in off-season vegetables: Effects on income and pesticide use in Bangladesh. *Food Policy*, 61, 132-140.
 104. Seldadyo, H., & Haan, J. (2006). The determinants of corruption: A literature survey and new evidence. *EPCS Conference*, 20-23.
 105. Shabbir, M. S. (2021). The Role of Islamic Microfinance Approach for Community Development. *Journal of Economics & Management Research*. SRC/JESMR/134. DOI: doi.org/10.47363/JESMR/2021 (2), 127.
 106. Shabbir, M. S. (2016). The role of formal academician in the promotion of microfinance. *International Journal of Research*, 4(5), 35-50
 107. Shabbir, M. S. (2018). Innovation Strategy of McDonald Business from Historical perspectives. *Innovative Journal of Business and Management*, 7(12), 30-41. 1
 108. Shabbir, M. S., Rehman, A. K., & Rasool, A. (2015). Does Islamic finance industry manage Shariah complaint risk in transactions. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 3(83), 59-66. 8
 109. Shabbir, M. S., Said, L. R., Pelit, I., & Irmak, E. (2023). The dynamic relationship among domestic stock returns volatility, oil prices, exchange rate and macroeconomic factors of investment. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 13(3), 560-565.
 110. Shabbir, M. S., Jabeen, M., Aziz, S., Abbasi, D. R. B. A., & Gul, A. (2020). Effects of E-Marketing on Growth of Businesses: Evidence from Pakistani Markets. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(7), 2128-2140.
 111. Shabbir, M. S., & Wisdom, O. (2020). The relationship between corporate social responsibility, environmental investments and financial performance: evidence from manufacturing companies. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 1-12. DOI: 10.1007/s11356-020-10217-0
 112. Shabbir, M.S. (2016), "The impact of financial development on the economic growth of Pakistan economy", *American Based Research journal*, Vol. 5 No. 3, pp. 35-43
 113. Sikandar, H., Kohar, U. H. A., Corzo-Palomo, E. E., Gamero-Huarcaya, V. K., Ramos-Meza, C. S., Shabbir, M. S., & Jain, V. (2023). Mapping the Development of Open Innovation Research in Business and Management Field: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1-23.
 114. Sikandar, H., Kohar, U.H.A., Sanda, G. et al. (2023). Eco-innovation in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): a Systematic Literature Review. *J Knowl Econ*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01367-w>
 115. Smith-Hillman, A. V. (2007). Competition policy, inflation and corruption: evidence from African economies. *Applied Economics Letters*, 14(9), 653-656.
 116. Stephen., P., Heyneman., Kathryn., H., Anderson., & Nazym., N. (2007). The Cost of Corruption in Higher Education. *Comparative Education Review*, 52(1), 1-25.
 117. Sulemana, I., & Kpienbaareh, D. (2018). An empirical examination of the relationship between income inequality and corruption in Africa. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 60, 27-42.
 118. Swaleheen, M. (2011). Economic growth with endogenous corruption: an empirical study. *Public Choice*, 146(1-2), 23-41.
 119. Saha, S., & Sen, K. (2023). Do economic and political crises lead to corruption? The role of

- institutions. *Economic Modelling*, 124, 106307.
120. Tabasam, A. H., Ashiq, A., Khan, M. N., Hafeez, S., Shabbir, M. S., & Zamir, A. (2022). Does technology improve customer satisfaction and loyalty? A comparative study of Islamic and conventional banks. *Journal of Management Info*, 9(2), 158-173
 121. Tankebe, J., & Asif, M. (2016). Police legitimacy and support for vigilante violence in Pakistan. *International Journal of Comparative and Applied Criminal Justice*, 40(4), 295-314.
 122. Tanzi, V., & Davoodi, H. (1997). Corruption, public investment, and growth. *Social Science Electronic Publishing . WP/ 97/139*.
 123. Theo., E., Cecilia., G., & Tanguy., v., Ypersele. (2009). Education, corruption, and the distribution of income. *Journal of Political Economy*, 14(3), 205-231.
 124. Truex, R. (2011). Corruption, Attitudes, and Education: Survey Evidence from Nepal. *World development*, 39(7), 1133-1142.
 125. Uddin, I., & Rahman, K. U. (2023). Impact of corruption, unemployment and inflation on economic growth evidence from developing countries. *Quality & Quantity*, 57(3), 2759-2779.
 126. Virta, H. (2010). The linkage between corruption and shadow economy size: does geography matter? *International Journal of Development Issues*, 9(1), 4-24.
 127. Ur Rehman, A., Aslam, E., Muhammad, R. S., Aslam, M., Iqbal, A., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). Consumer Awareness And Knowledge About Takaful (Islamic Insurance): A Survey Of Pakistan. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 35, 4101-4118.
 128. Wa Githinji, M., & Adesida, O. (2011). Industrialization, exports and the developmental State in Africa: The case for transformation: University of Massachusetts Amherst, Department of Economics.
 129. Wade, R. Irrigation reform in conditions of populist anarchy: An Indian case. 14(3), 0-303.
 130. Wang, J., Ramzan, M., Makin, F., Mahmood, C. K., Ramos-Meza, C. S., Jain, V., & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). Does clean energy matter? The dynamic effects of different strategies of renewable energy, carbon emissions, and trade openness on sustainable economic growth. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-10.
 131. Westerlund, J., & Edgerton, D. L. (2007). A panel bootstrap cointegration test. *Economics Letters*, 97(3), 185-190.
 132. Wright, S. J., Sanchezazofeifa, G. A., Portilloquintero, C., & Davies, D. (2007). Poverty and corruption compromise tropical forest reserves. *Ecological Applications*, 17(5), 1259-1266.
 133. Xue, M., Mihai, D., Brutu, M., Popescu, L., Sinisi, C., Bansal, A., Mohammad, M., Muhammad, T. & Shabbir, M. (2024). Examining the Impact of Energy Policies on CO2 Emissions with Information and Communication Technologies and Renewable Energy. *Studies in Nonlinear Dynamics & Econometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/snde-2022-0065>
 134. Yan, X., Abdalla, A. A., Zhu, G., Uslu, Y. D., Mohamed, M. A. A., Muhammad, T., & Shabbir, M. S. (2024). Does natural resources matter? Nexus among renewable energy policies, technological innovation, environmental protection, and economic growth. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 51, 101272.
 135. Zalanga, S. (2018). The Political Economy of Corruption. *Working Papers*, 42(4), 561-562.
 136. Zazueta, I. M. S., & Cortez, W. W. (2019). The impact of political alternation on corruption in Mexico. *Revista de Ciencia Política*, 35(2), 371-392.
 137. Zhang, M., Jain, V., Qian, X., Ramos-Meza, C. S., Ali, S. A., Sharma, P., ... & Shabbir, M. S. (2023). The dynamic relationship among technological innovation, international trade, and energy production. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 967138.